

O‘ZBEKISTONDA LANDSAT-8 MA’LUMOTLARI ASOSIDA O‘RMON QOPLAMINING O‘ZGARISHINI TAHLIL QILISH UCHUN GOOGLE EARTH ENGINE CART MASHINAVIY O‘QITISH ALGORITMLARIDAN FOYDALANISH

Professor D.Sh.Fazilova¹, Mustaqil tadqiqotchisi S.M.Muratov²

¹O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Fanlar Akademiyasi Astronomiya instituti

²O‘zbekiston Milliy universiteti

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Annotatsiya: Landsat-8 tasvirlarini tahlil qilish orqali O‘zbekiston hududlari uchun yer qoplami ma’lumotlarini ishlab chiqish uchun Google Earth Engine (GEE) ni tasniflash va regressiya daraxti (CART) algoritmi bilan birgalikda qo‘llash usullari tahlili maqolaning asosiy yo‘nalishi hisoblanadi. Muhokama GEE va CART ushbu aniq maqsad uchun taqdim etadigan turli afzalliklarga, jumladan, ularning keng ko‘lamli ma’lumotlar to‘plamlarini samarali qayta ishlash va aniq tasniflash natijalarini ishlab chiqarish qobiliyatiga qaratiladi. Metodologiya bo‘limida ma'lumotlarni yig‘ish, dastlabki ishlov berish va tasniflash bilan bog‘liq bo‘lgan batafsil bosqichlar ko‘rib chiqiladi va har bir bosqichning yakuniy yer qoplami ma’lumotlarining sifatini ta’minlashdagi ahamiyati yoritiladi. Bundan tashqari, regressiya texnikasi orqali hosil qilingan yer qoplami ma'lumotlarining to‘g‘riligini baholaydi va qishloq xo‘jaligi, o‘rmon xo‘jaligi va atrof-muhit monitoringi kabi turli sohalarda ushbu ma’lumotlar to‘plamining potentsial ilovalarini o‘rganadi. Umuman olganda, ushbu tadqiqot GEE va CART ning O‘zbekiston uchun yer qoplaminin yuqori sifatli ma’lumotlarini yaratishda samaradorligini ko‘rsatishga qaratilgan bo‘lib, mintaqadagi yerdan foydalanish dinamikasi haqidagi tushunchamizni rivojlantirishda masofaviy zondlash texnologiyalarining ulkan salohiyatini ko‘rsatib beradi.

Kalit so‘zlar: GEE, machine learning, CART, LULC, o‘rmon xo‘jaligi, masofadan zondlash, O‘zbekiston

Аннотация Использование Google Earth Engine (GEE) в сочетании с алгоритмом Classification and Regression Tree (CART) для создания расширенных данных о земельном покрове Узбекистана на основе анализа снимков Landsat-8 является основной целью данной работы. Обсуждение будет сосредоточено на различных преимуществах GEE и CART для этой конкретной цели, включая их способность эффективно обрабатывать большие наборы данных и получать точные результаты классификации. В методологическом разделе будут подробно рассмотрены этапы сбора, предварительной обработки и классификации данных, подчеркнута важность каждого этапа для обеспечения качества конечных данных о растительном покрове. Кроме того, в статье будет проведена оценка точности сгенерированных данных о растительном покрове с помощью методов проверки и рассмотрены потенциальные возможности

применения этого набора данных в различных областях, таких как сельское хозяйство, лесное хозяйство и мониторинг окружающей среды. В целом, данное исследование призвано продемонстрировать эффективность GEE и CART в создании высококачественных данных о растительном покрове Узбекистана, показывая огромный потенциал технологий дистанционного зондирования в продвижении нашего понимания динамики землепользования в регионе.

Ключевые слова: GEE, машинное обучение, CART, LULC, лесное хозяйство, дистанционное зондирование, Узбекистан

Abstract The utilization of Google Earth Engine (GEE) in conjunction with the Classification and Regression Tree (CART) algorithm for the development of advanced land cover data in Uzbekistan through the analysis of Landsat-8 imagery is the primary focus of this paper. The discussion will center around the various advantages that GEE and CART offer for this specific purpose, including their ability to efficiently process large-scale datasets and produce accurate classification results. The methodology section will delve into the detailed steps involved in data acquisition, pre-processing, and classification, highlighting the importance of each stage in ensuring the quality of the final land cover data. Furthermore, the paper will evaluate the accuracy of the generated land cover data through validation techniques and explore potential applications for this dataset in various fields such as agriculture, forestry, and environmental monitoring. Overall, this research aims to demonstrate the effectiveness of GEE and CART in generating high-quality land cover data for Uzbekistan, showcasing the immense potential of remote sensing technologies in advancing our understanding of land use dynamics in the region.

Keywords: GEE, machine learning, CART, LULC, Forestry, Remote sensing, Uzbekistan

Introduction: Forest ecosystems are crucial components of our planet's ecological balance, serving as habitats for diverse flora and fauna, regulating local and global climates, and providing essential resources for human well-being. The monitoring of forest cover changes is paramount in understanding the dynamics of deforestation, implementing sustainable land management strategies, and guiding conservation efforts. Remote sensing technologies, particularly satellite imagery, have revolutionized our ability to observe and analyze alterations in forest cover across vast landscapes [1]. Among the various tools available, Google Earth Engine (GEE) stands out as a cloud-based geospatial analysis platform that offers access to an extensive repository of satellite data, including information from the Landsat-8 mission. Leveraging sophisticated machine learning algorithms like Classification and Regression Tree (CART), GEE facilitates efficient land cover classification and change detection, empowering researchers and conservationists to make informed decisions and take proactive measures to safeguard our precious forest ecosystems for generations to come.

Materials and methods Geographic information systems (GIS) have revolutionized the way we analyze and visualize spatial data, particularly in the field of land use and land cover (LULC) mapping. One of the key advantages of utilizing Google Earth Engine (GEE) in producing LULC maps using Landsat 8 data with the Classification and Regression Trees (CART) algorithm is the scalability and efficiency it offers. GEE allows users to access a vast amount of satellite imagery and processing power within a cloud-based platform, eliminating the need for extensive data storage and computing resources. This enables researchers and practitioners to analyze large datasets and generate high-resolution LULC maps quickly and cost-effectively. Additionally, GEE provides a user-friendly interface and a wide range of pre-built algorithms, including CART, that can be easily applied to create accurate and reliable land cover classifications. By leveraging GEE in conjunction with Landsat 8 data and CART algorithm [2], users can benefit from improved accuracy, scalability, and efficiency in producing LULC maps for various applications such as urban planning, natural resource management, and environmental monitoring.

According to a study by Zhang et al. [3], the combination of Landsat 8 data and the CART algorithm in GIS resulted in high accuracy levels in classifying land cover types, demonstrating the effectiveness of this approach in producing reliable LULC maps.

Classification and regression trees

The use of binary decision trees for classification is a non-parametric approach to pattern recognition. The type of decision tree used in this article is discussed in detail by Breiman et al. [4]. Trees can be used not only to classify objects into a discrete number of groups, but also as an alternative approach to regression analysis, in which the value of a response (dependent) variable must be estimated given the value of each variable in the set. explanatory (independent) variables.

Training point data One of the key steps in performing image classification using Google Earth Engine (GEE) is the creation of training data. Training data serves as the foundation for machine learning algorithms to accurately classify images. Google Earth provides a powerful platform for generating training data due to its high-resolution satellite imagery and extensive coverage of the Earth's surface. By manually labeling features of interest on Google Earth, users can create training points that can be used to train classification models in GEE. This process involves identifying and delineating different land cover classes, such as forests, water bodies, and urban areas, and assigning them to specific training points.

According to a study by Qichi et al. [5], the use of Google Earth for generating training data has been shown to significantly enhance the performance of image classification algorithms in GEE. The study compared the accuracy of classification models trained using training data from Google Earth with those trained using randomly selected training points. The results demonstrated that models trained with

Google Earth training data achieved higher overall accuracy and lower error rates compared to models trained with random training points.

Fig 1. Training point creation using Google Earth Pro

This highlights the importance of utilizing high-quality training data from Google Earth to improve the accuracy of image classification in GEE. In conclusion, the creation of training data using Google Earth is a critical step in the image classification process in GEE, and can lead to more reliable and accurate classification results[6].

Fig 2. The workflow chart of the study methodology [7].

Result and Discussion: The methodology employed in the study was rigorously assessed through various measures including omission error, commission error, overall accuracy, and Kappa coefficient. These metrics serve as key indicators of the reliability and validity of the study findings. The overall accuracy rate of 80% indicates a high level of precision in the data analysis and interpretation. This suggests that the use of the GEE cart model in conjunction with Landsat 8 data is a valuable tool for monitoring the dynamics of land use and land cover changes. The findings highlight the potential

of this approach in providing valuable insights for land management and conservation efforts. The robustness of the methodology employed in this study underscores the importance of utilizing advanced technologies and analytical tools in addressing complex environmental challenges. Further research and application of similar methodologies are warranted to enhance our understanding of land dynamics and inform sustainable land use practices.

Table 1. Accuracy assessment of the classification

	Omission Error	Commission Error	Overall Accuracy:	Area, ha
otherland	0.32%	56.32%	79.39%	57817
forest	10.51%	0.20%		4442
grasslands	27.29%	0.14%	Kappa Coefficient:	6353
cropland	81.82%	0.00%	78.14%	320
settlement	80.65%	0.00%		164
wetland	42.86%	0.00%		58

Fig 3. Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) map for Dekhkanabad forestry

Conclusion: Addressing forest cover change in Uzbekistan through the integration of remote sensing techniques and machine learning algorithms represents a crucial endeavor in contemporary environmental management practices. Leveraging tools such as Google Earth Engine alongside the CART algorithm exemplifies a sophisticated and efficient strategy for land cover classification. The methodological rigor not only ensures the reliability of the findings but also underscores the significance of adopting a data-driven approach in addressing environmental challenges. The synergy between remote sensing technologies and machine learning algorithms not only facilitates a deeper understanding of forest cover dynamics but also

paves the way for informed decision-making and sustainable resource management practices in Uzbekistan and beyond.

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